

RANDOM		HUMAN	
success	unsuccess	success	unsuccess
3	0	5	0
6	0	7	0
1	0	10	0
7	0	13	0
7	0	12	0
5	0	6	0
2	0	9	0
3	0	10	0
7	0	7	0
2	0	12	0
4	0	6	0
8	0	7	0
6	0	8	0
2	0	10	0
2	0	3	0
9	0	4	0
3	0	9	0
2	0	7	0
3	0	11	0
5	0	5	0
5	0	7	0
7	0	6	0
2	0	11	0
6	0	16	0
8	0	10	0
7	0	6	0
2	0	11	0
3	0	11	0
6	0	8	0
9	0	3	0
RAND success	RAND unsuccess	HUMAN success	HUMAN unsuccess
142	0	250	0

RANDOM		HUMAN	
success	unsuccess	success	unsuccess
3	0	8	0
7	0	13	0
3	0	6	0
5	0	8	0
4	0	9	0
2	0	10	0
9	0	6	0
5	0	7	0
7	0	7	0
7	0	10	0
1	0	6	0
6	0	12	0
11	0	5	0
3	0	10	0
6	0	4	0
4	0	9	0
0	0	9	0
7	0	12	0
2	0	10	0
6	0	4	0
8	0	11	0
1	0	9	0
3	0	9	0
5	0	6	0
3	0	6	0
7	0	7	0
7	0	11	0
3	0	10	0
8	0	2	0
9	0	9	0
RAND success	RAND unsuccess	HUMAN success	HUMAN unsuccess
152	0	245	0

RANDOM		HUMAN	
RAND success	RAND unsuccess	HUMAN success	HUMAN unsuccess
2	3	6	0
1	0	5	0
3	5	9	0
7	3	6	0
6	2	12	0
4	3	7	0
7	8	5	0
3	0	9	0
7	9	7	0
8	0	6	0
2	1	8	0
4	7	7	0
3	6	9	0
5	6	7	0
1	2	3	0
8	9	7	0
3	4	5	0
6	6	7	0
5	4	3	0
3	2	5	0
4	2	8	0
4	0	10	0
3	3	5	0
9	10	11	0
6	2	9	0
6	4	8	0
4	2	8	0
4	1	2	0
3	1	12	0
7	3	9	0
RAND success	RAND unsuccess	HUMAN success	HUMAN unsuccess
138	108	215	0

	RANDOM		HUMAN		
	RAND success	RAND unsuccess	HUMAN success	HUMAN unsuccess	
1	11	20	5	0	
2	2	3	9	0	
3	4	6	9	0	
4	6	12	4	0	
5	6	18	6	0	
6	6	19	6	0	
7	7	13	9	0	
8	2	2	12	0	
9	10	19	10	0	
10	4	10	11	0	
11	10	27	17	0	
12	6	13	7	0	
13	5	8	15	0	
14	4	3	6	0	
15	9	14	7	1	
16	6	9	10	0	
17	3	6	8	0	
18	7	16	16	0	
19	9	17	7	0	
20	6	2	9	0	
21	5	9	6	0	
22	4	12	12	0	
23	6	10	5	0	
24	8	20	12	0	
25	9	19	7	0	
26	7	16	12	0	
27	6	4	7	0	
28	4	10	10	0	
29	2	2	12	0	
30	3	5	7	0	
	RAND success	RAND unsuccess	HUMAN success	HUMAN unsuccess	
	177	344	273	1	

RANDOM		HUMAN	
success	unsuccess	success	unsuccess
3	4	12	0
4	13	3	0
4	17	13	0
5	2	11	0
4	5	7	0
3	11	12	0
4	3	9	0
6	13	5	0
3	7	7	0
5	10	7	0
5	7	8	0
3	9	9	0
2	11	6	0
6	9	8	0
4	7	2	0
2	5	8	0
6	14	9	0
4	5	6	0
5	8	8	0
4	7	14	1
4	7	7	0
5	12	9	0
6	12	11	0
3	5	7	0
2	6	9	0
6	7	10	0
4	12	5	0
5	14	9	0
5	17	10	0
3	7	10	1
RAND success	RAND unsuccess	HUMAN success	HUMAN unsuccess
125	266	251	2

	RANDOM		HUMAN		
	RAND success	RAND unsuccess	HUMAN success	HUMAN unsuccess	
1	9	21	8	0	
2	4	14	10	0	
3	7	11	5	0	
4	4	6	6	0	
5	4	10	8	0	
6	5	13	4	0	
7	2	2	9	0	
8	3	3	9	0	
9	2	4	11	0	
10	11	13	8	0	
11	3	11	5	0	
12	9	14	6	0	
13	4	3	7	0	
14	2	4	9	0	
15	2	3	7	0	
16	3	10	7	0	
17	4	13	12	0	
18	4	5	6	0	
19	3	6	13	0	
20	3	9	5	0	
21	5	8	9	0	
22	0	0	7	0	
23	4	3	11	0	
24	8	6	6	0	
25	6	5	9	0	
26	3	2	8	0	
27	2	3	7	0	
28	2	4	9	0	
29	7	5	4	0	
30	3	3	9	0	
	RAND success	RAND unsuccess	HUMAN success	HUMAN unsuccess	
	128	214	234	0	

RANDOM		HUMAN																		
success	unsuccess	success	unsuccess																	
0	2	11	0																	
3	4	7	0																	
0	1	8	0																	
1	1	5	0																	
1	0	7	0																	
2	4	8	0																	
2	4	12	0																	
3	4	11	0																	
1	5	7	0																	
3	2	7	0																	
1	2	12	0																	
1	2	9	0																	
0	4	8	0																	
0	0	3	0																	
3	3	6	0																	
3	7	10	0																	
2	1	4	0																	
1	5	7	0																	
1	3	4	0																	
1	5	13	0																	
3	4	8	0																	
3	2	5	0																	
2	5	4	0																	
1	7	7	0																	
1	6	10	0																	
0	4	4	0																	
2	0	12	0																	
2	5	4	0																	
0	2	15	0																	
3	10	6	0																	
RAND success	RAND unsuccess	HUMAN success	HUMAN unsuccess																	
46	104	234	0																	

	success percentages	
	random	human
openaccount	100,00%	100,00%
updateprofile	100,00%	100,00%
transfer	56,10%	100,00%
contact	33,97%	99,64%
billpay	31,97%	99,21%
findtrans	37,43%	100,00%
requestloan	30,67%	100,00%
AVERAGE	55,73%	99,83%